

Effect of Self-Management Technique on Aggressive Tendency Among Secondary School Students in Nnewi North Local Government Area of Anambra State

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Abstract

This study investigated the Effect of Self-Management Technique on Aggressive Tendency among Secondary School Students in Nnewi North Local Government Area of Anambra State. Three research questions guided the study, while three hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Quasi-experimental research design was adopted for this study. The population for this study was a total of 873 junior and senior (JSS2 and SS2) aggressive tendency students from all public secondary schools in Nnewi North. Research sample consisted of 80 students with the highest test scores in the aggressive tendency measuring instrument selected through purposive sampling technique. The Researchers used an instrument called Aggressive Tendency Questionnaire (ATQ) for collection of data for this study. Data collected from this study were analysed using mean and ANCOVA. Results obtained from the study indicated that self-management technique was effective in reducing aggressive tendency among the participants. The results equally showed that self-management technique was more effective in reducing aggressive tendency among the female participants than their male counterparts. Also, the results indicated that self-management technique was more effective in reducing aggressive tendency among the senior students who participated in the experiment than their junior counterpart. Furthermore, the results indicated that there was a significant decrease in aggressive tendency among students in the experimental group when compared with those in the control group. However, the difference in the effects of self-management technique on students' aggressive tendency was not significant based on gender and age. Based on the findings of this study, some recommendations were made. The researchers recommended, among others, that self-management technique should be adopted by counsellors and other helping professionals as an effective counselling technique in reducing secondary school students' aggressive tendency. School counsellors should therefore ensure that they acquire adequate knowledge of the technique so as to be able to help students with aggressive tendency effectively.

Key words: *Effect, Self-management, Technique, Aggressive tendency*

Introduction

The global drift of aggressive acts among secondary school students today calls for serious concern. The increasing rate of aggression and violence in our present society demands immediate intervention procedures. In the past, secondary school students were seen and known to be well behaved, properly nurtured and brought up, but nowadays the reverse is the trend as they are often involved in one form of aggressive behaviour or the other. The school environment is no longer safe and conducive for teaching and learning activities because of the prevalence of aggressive tendency among students. Bullying, hooliganism, rape, robbery, and so on, which are subsets of aggression, are often in display by angry and uncultured students within the school premises. Ojewola (2014) lamented that in the olden days teachers were confronted with minor disciplinary problems such as chewing gum, talking out of turn or making a noise, while in the present days, teachers are confronted with higher disciplinary problems such as bullying, rape, cultism, robbery, drug addiction, assault, among others.

Aggression has often been defined as an action or response by an individual to harm or cause something unpleasant to another person. DeWall, Anderson and Bushman (2012) defined aggression as a behaviour that is intended to harm another person who is motivated to avoid that harm. According to Krahe (2013), aggression is defined as any behaviour directed toward another individual that is carried out with the intent to cause harm. Aggression is a hostile, injurious or destructive behaviour or outlook especially when caused by frustration (Merriam-Webster, 2015). In the context of this study, aggression is defined as antisocial behaviour which is intended to hurt or inflict pain on another person or group of persons. It consists of actions, words, or attitudes that are capable of preventing people from peaceful and harmonious living. This harm can take many forms such as physical injury, hurt feelings, or damaged social relationships (to name just a few). In addition, the perpetrator must believe that the action will harm the target, and that the target is motivated to avoid the action.

In the present times, little acts of aggression and misunderstanding have led to serious inter-school crisis and turmoil (Ojewola, 2009). Pages of national and international dailies are filled with issues of violence and aggression among students. Most times, inter-school debates and sport competitions have caused serious crisis among students which have led to loss of lives and property. The situation calls for urgent intervention, especially the use of more robust scientific procedure such as self-management technique that could reduce aggressive tendency among students. The media (Print and broadcast) are frequently filled with reports of violence and aggression among adolescents. Hence, Yousset, Attia and Kamel (2015) emphasized that involvement in physical fighting is very common in many parts of the world among secondary school students.

Aggressive tendency may be defined as the predisposed intent to harm or inflict injury to another person. According to Nyoman, Wayan and Ni (2017), aggressive tendency is the predisposition to use force

or power to cause harm to oneself, another person or group of persons. However, in the context of this study, aggression tendency is defined as a high possibility, disposition or likelihood that a student would inflict pain on other students just to derive pleasure. Aggressive tendency is a negative attitude that affects character formation of a student. It may also negatively affect quality teaching and learning of students in classroom. Hence, Akilu (2013) established that disagreement and conflicts in a teaching and learning situation affect achievement level of students. Aggressive tendency appears replete among secondary school students. According to Shekarey, Ladani and Rostami (2013), aggressive tendency is common in secondary schools. In the same vein, Aluede (2011) stated that aggression in schools has become more prominent in the last few years, as news articles about aggression and violent acts within the secondary school setting are on the increase. Aggression among secondary school students is an issue of concern among stakeholders in education essentially because a school is an institution designed for teaching and learning. Unarguably, effective teaching and learning can only successfully take place in a conducive environment devoid of intimidation, harassment, insecurity and fear. Unfortunately, the use of weapons such as knives, dagger, bottles, axes and even guns by students for fighting has become the order of the day in the modern day secondary schools.

Many students sustain injuries during such clashes. Physical fight between one student and the other including bullying are frequent occurrences in secondary schools. According to Aluede (2011), bullying (a subcategory of aggressive tendency) is encountered regularly by children and adolescents in the context of schools worldwide. Consequently, schools are no longer safe for academic work because violence and aggression have become the order of the day there. Many students go to school with charms and arms. Little quarrels and misunderstanding have often led to destruction of lives and properties in schools and the society. This is further buttressed by the report of Flisher (2016), that in Cape Town South Africa 9.8% of males, and 1.3% of females in secondary schools were reported carrying knives to schools in a period of four weeks. Similarly, in Scotland, about 34.1% of male and 8.6% of female students (11-16 years old) agreed that they had carried weapons to school at least once (Mckeganey & Norrie, 2014).

Secondary school students' aggressive tendency can develop in different ways. Some children exhibit behavioural problem in early childhood that gradually escalates to severe forms of aggression before and during adolescent (Huizinga, Loeber & Thornbery, 2015). Stattin and Magnusson (2009) noted that childhood aggression is a good predictor of violence in adolescent and early adulthood. According to Pulkkinen (2012) and Farrington (2014), in a follow up study in Finland, of nearly 400 youths, aggression at the ages of 8 and 14 years significantly predicted aggression in later ages. Longitudinal researches that monitored individuals from childhood through adolescence and into adulthood found very high correlations between behavioural problems at one time and aggressive behaviours later in their lives of those (Farrington, 2014; Lahey, 2009). Many aggressive and violent adolescents may grow up to become adults with antisocial personality disorders, and thus continue in their aggressive and criminal behaviours throughout their live time.

It is generally believed that modern societies are becoming unnecessarily aggressive and violent. Infact, it is horrifying to witness the level of violence and aggression by adolescents or even younger children in the societies today. In addition, aggressive tendency may cause harm to the physical, psychological, social and academic wellbeing of students. Aggressive tendency among students may result to adjustment difficulties which may lead to poor academic achievement and subsequent withdrawal from school. It could also result to delinquent acts such as bullying, cultism, robbery, rape, destruction of private and public properties, and disposition to other serious criminal activities. School authorities and other stakeholders have put in place measures such as corporal punishment, suspension, expulsion, among others to curb aggression in secondary schools. However, these measures have not yielded much success as the level of aggressive tendency among students is still alarming.

This situation has therefore become worrisome to stakeholders such as teachers, parents, Counsellors, school administrators and the society at large. Against this backdrop, it is very imperative to explore good behavioural intervention strategies such self-management technique to help curb the problem of aggressive tendency among secondary school students so that they can live in peace and harmony with themselves and other people around. Achieving this will help bring the school back to its former state of being a safe place where students can function to their full potentials. Betiku (2013) emphasized that behavioural intervention strategies such as self-management technique have the capacity for guiding individuals towards developing new and acceptable behaviours.

Self-management technique is a technique derived from the cognitive learning theory (Olwens, 2007). It is a behaviour modification strategy in which people are taught to discriminate their own target behaviour and record the occurrence or absence of that target behaviour (Buckmann, 2015). According to Oguzie, Obi and Nnadi (2019), self-management technique is defined as a behaviour intervention strategy which is used to help clients to achieve adequate self-awareness and self control. Self-management technique is used to assist individuals with maladaptive behaviours, such as aggressive tendency, anger, shyness, bullying, anxiety, among others, to achieve greater levels of independence in personal-social and academic activities. Self management technique could also play an important role in character formation and behaviour modification of secondary school students (Ganz, 2008). Self-management technique has emerged as an effective approach for improving classroom behaviour (Barry & Messer, 2008). Ekwe and Nwamuo (2011) emphasized that it is imperative that the students are trained in self-management so as to enable them take control of their activities and acquire self-regulatory capacity over their behaviours. Studies have indicated that self management has shown positive outcomes for students with a wide variety of disabilities such as learning disabilities, speech and language impairments, intellectual disabilities, emotional and or behavioural disorders, attention-deficit, and hyperactivity (Sincalvin, Calvin, Wehmeyer & Hughes, 2005). Self management technique constitutes behavioural strategies through which a person directs and upholds his unwanted behaviour in order to produce desirable effects. It has been variously named self regulation, self control, and self restraint methods because, it is the process by which a person

observes and records some of his or her own behaviours that need to be changed. Self management is the individual's effort to evaluate him or herself against a self-selected standard as yardstick for good behaviour in the society.

However, in context of this study, self management technique is defined as a behaviour intervention strategy used in helping students to make efforts in evaluating, controlling and monitoring their aggressive tendency for improvement towards acceptable character in their schools and the society in general. By learning self-management skills students can become more self-directed and less dependent on continuous supervision. Operationally, during self management therapy, the Counsellor teaches the students strategies (such as self-monitoring, self-control, self-recording, self-reward and self punishment) which make it necessary for students with aggression tendency to examine the type of behaviours they exhibit toward themselves and people around them and also consider the consequences of such behaviours. The modification of thought pattern is the goal of this treatment strategy and as such the researcher believes that this technique if applied will serve as a veritable tool in reducing aggressive tendency among secondary school students.

Gender and age have been reported as factors that moderate aggressive tendency among secondary school students (McCall & Shields, 2008; Oguzie, Obi & Nnadi, 2019). Researchers like Lansford, Sorbring and Bornstein (2012) observed that aggressive tendency is more among male students than female students. Lansford and his group further stated that female students are more likely to gain in intervention strategies on aggressive tendency than their male counterparts. Age has also been reported as another factor that moderates aggressive tendency in human beings (Bongers, Koot & Jans, 2014). In their research Sameer and Jamia (2007) found that SSS students have greater level of aggressive tendency, and are likely to benefit more during intervention treatments than the junior students. Similarly, Omoteso (2010) found that older students bully younger ones. This study therefore ascertained the moderating effects of gender and age so as know whether the above reported findings would be the same with the findings of this study.

Statement of Problem

Aggression in Nigeria has been a perturbing issue to all and sundry due to the frightening increase in aggressive acts such as kidnapping of foreigners and prominent citizens including suicidal attacks on schools, government establishments, banks, and churches. Today in Nigeria, many people live in fear because of the increasing rate of aggressive activities on the entire populace manifesting in extortion, bullying, rape, robbery, kidnapping, terrorism, and so on. Secondary school students are not left out of this ugly menace. They are not only vulnerable but can be directly or indirectly affected when their parents and relatives are involved. Oftentimes, secondary school students have been kidnapped and held hostage for ransom and their parents have also suffered various forms of aggression. Recently, people noted with shock the spread of aggressive activities in schools and the wider society. For instance, on the 27th of September

2010, the whole nation woke up with the shocking news of the abduction of 15 children in Aba, Abia State. Again, 200 secondary school students were abducted in Chibok, Borno State. Also, the rampant cases of killings and maiming of innocent citizens by the Fulani Herdsmen have kept the whole nation, including secondary school students in fears.

Consequently, aggression has without doubt become a common feature and a nightmare in secondary schools both in Anambra state and Nigeria in general. Although the school had always remained one of the safest places, next to the home in a student's life, one wonders if this still holds true in the contemporary secondary school situation given the ever increasing spate of aggressive acts among secondary school students. The school which is expected to have been a safe heaven, a place where students should feel safe and secured has become a battle ground because of aggressive activities. Aggression like a wild wind that blows no one any good is a problem to the aggressors, victims and the society in general. Aggression may cause severe threat to students' safety and security, which could result to absenteeism, poor performance and achievement, school dropout, and so on. In fact, aggressive tendency may have negative effects on the social, psychological and academic well-being of students. In addition, students with aggressive tendency may develop into adult criminals, cultists, assassins, kidnappers or militants who will cause mayhem to other people and mar the peace and security of the entire nation.

The high incidence of aggression in secondary schools is so worrisome because it may impact negatively on the student's right to human dignity, privacy, freedom and security. Unarguably, students are expected to relate well and leave in peace and harmony with their fellow students, teachers and other people in the school and society at large. Unfortunately, the reality seems to be that only few students can harmoniously blend with their school mates and other people around them as a result of aggressive tendency. This therefore makes it very glaring that the physical, emotional and educational consequences of aggressive tendency among secondary school students cannot be underestimated. Aggressive tendency has in fact become a threat that no school can afford to disregard.

Despite the increasing rate of aggressive tendency among students, the society still expects that schools should continue to be safe place for students. Thus, in order to maintain a peaceful and safe school environment, stakeholders in education have tended to solve the problem of aggressive tendency among students by putting in place measures such as corporal punishment, suspension, expulsion, among others. However, such measures seem to have not yielded the desired result since the problem of aggression tendency among students is still remaining unabated. Aggressive tendency among secondary school students is therefore a big problem that needs an urgent attention and if left unchecked may transform to much more antisocial problems that are capable of affecting every member of the society in the nearest future. The above scenario thus called for the use of behavioural intervention measures in solving the problem of aggressive tendency among students. This therefore formed the problem that motivated the researcher to embark on this study.

Research questions

The study was guided by the following research questions.

1. What is the effect of self-management technique on aggressive tendency of secondary school students when compared with those who received conventional counselling using their pretest and posttest scores?
2. What is the difference in the effects of self-management technique on aggressive tendency of male and female secondary school students using their pretest and posttest scores?
3. What is the difference in the effects of self-management technique on aggressive tendency of junior and senior secondary school students using their pretest and posttest scores?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 levels of significance:

1. The effect of self-management technique on aggressive tendency of secondary school students is not significant when compared with those treated with conventional counselling using their pretest and posttest scores.
2. There is no significant difference in the effects of self-management technique on aggressive tendency of male and female secondary school students using their pretest and posttest scores.
3. There is no significant difference in the effects of self-management technique on aggressive tendency of junior and senior secondary school students using their pretest and posttest scores.

Method

The research design used in this study was quasi experimental design. Akuezuiilo and Agu (2007) pointed out that quasi experimental research design could be used in school setting where it is not always possible to use pure experimental design which they consider as a disruption of school activities. It utilized the non- randomized pretest and post test control group design comprising two main groups (Experimental group I and Control group) using two treatment groups.

The study was conducted in Nnewi North Local Government Area of Anambra State. The population of this study was 873 students. This comprised of Junior Secondary Students (JSS2) and Senior Secondary Students (SS2) from the eight co-educational secondary schools in Nnewi North local government area with aggressive tendency. The students' population was identified through a pretest administration of the Aggressive Tendency Questionnaire (ATQ). Students found to have aggressive tendency constituted the population, that is, students that scored above the baseline of 65. The sample for the study was 80 students. This comprises students from junior and senior secondary schools (JSS II and SS II) that were identified with aggressive tendency from two (2) selected co-educational secondary schools.

The instrument that was used for measuring student's aggressive tendency was an Aggression Tendency Questionnaire (ATQ) originally developed in 2000 by Buss and Warren. Aggression Tendency Questionnaire report psychometric scale which was developed to measure individual's aggressive tendency

as it relates to social setting and peers. The Aggression Questionnaire for this study has two sections: A and B. Section A is an introductory part that solicited the bio-data of the respondents and section B is directed towards measuring students' level of aggressive tendency. The respondents were required to indicate by ticking (√) how often they experience certain feelings, thought and actions.

The instrument contains 34 items on a five-point scale ranging from 1=Not at all like me; 2=A little like me; 3=Somewhat like me; 4=Very much like me;5=Completely like me. The instrument was validated by Buss and Warren in 2000, and has both face and construct validity. Buss and Warren in 2000 obtained a cronbach alpha internal consistency reliability coefficient of 0.81. The researchers therefore adopted the instrument without further reliability estimation.

Students with high scores were considered to be having aggressive tendency and were assigned to both the experimental and control groups in equal proportion. A special request was made to the schools principals for the provision of adequate and conducive counselling centre for the administration of the questionnaire and during the period of treatment. The Aggression Tendency Questionnaire was administered to the students in the chosen secondary schools personally by the researcher, with the help of three research assistants. The research assistants collected the Aggression Questionnaire from the respondents and handed over to the researcher for scoring. The results from the first administered Aggression Tendency Questionnaire formed the pre-test scores while the results from the second administered Aggression Tendency Questionnaire formed the post-test scores. All responses for the twenty items on Aggression Tendency Questionnaire were summated to yield a total score.

The data collected for this study were analyzed with the arithmetic mean to answer the research questions and analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was used in testing the hypotheses at 0.05 levels of significance.

Results

Table 1 Pretest and Posttest scores of students treated with SMT and those treated with conventional counselling

Source of Variation	N	Pretest	Mean	Posttest Mean	Lost Mean	Remark
Self-management Tech.	40	132.93	98.85	34.08	Effective	
Control	40	129.90	119.15	10.75		

Table 1 reveals that the students treated with Self-management technique had pretest mean score of 132.93 and posttest mean score of 98.85 with lost mean 34.08 in their aggressive tendency scores, while those in the control group who were trained with conventional counselling had pretest mean score of 129.90 and posttest mean score of 119.15 with lost mean 10.75. Self-management technique is effective in reducing students' aggressive tendencies.

Table 2: Pretest and Posttest scores of male and female students treated with SMT

Source of Variation	N	Pretest Mean	Posttest Mean	Lost Mean	Remark
Male	20	131.80	98.85	32.95	
Female effective	20	134.05	98.85	35.20	More

In table 2, it was observed that the male students treated with Self-management technique had pretest mean score of 131.80 and posttest mean score of 98.85 with lost mean 32.95 in their aggressive tendency scores, while the female students treated with Self-management technique had pretest mean score of 134.05 and posttest mean score of 98.85 with lost mean 35.20 in their aggressive tendency scores. Therefore, self-management technique is more effective in reducing female students' aggressive tendencies.

Table 3: Pretest and Posttest scores of junior and senior students treated with SMT

Source of Variation	N	Pretest Mean	Posttest Mean	Lost Mean	Remark
Junior	20	131.65	98.75	32.90	
Senior	20	134.20	98.95	35.25	More effective

Table 3 indicates that the junior students treated with Self-management technique had pretest mean score of 131.65 and posttest mean score of 98.75 with lost mean 32.90 in their aggressive tendency scores, while the senior students treated with Self-management technique had pretest mean score of 134.20 and posttest mean score of 98.95 with lost mean 35.25 in their aggressive tendency scores. Therefore, self-management technique is more effective in reducing senior students' aggressive tendencies.

Table 4 ANCOVA on the effect of self-management technique on aggressive tendency of secondary school students compared with those treated with conventional counselling using their posttest scores

Source of variation	SS	df	MS	Cal. F	Pvalue	P ≤ 0.05
Corrected Model	9164.835	2	4582.418			
Intercept	1018.451	1	1018.451			
Pretest	923.035	1	923.035			
Treatment method	8973.736	1	8973.736	128.17	0.000	S
Error	5391.165	77	70.015			
Total	965036.000	80				
Corrected Total	14556.000	79				

In table 4, it was observed that at 0.05 level of significance, 1df numerator and 79df denominator, the calculated F is 128.17 with Pvalue of 0.000 which is less than 0.05. Therefore, the first null hypothesis is rejected. So, the effect of self-management technique on aggressive tendency of secondary school students is significant.

Table 5 ANCOVA on the effectiveness of self-management technique on aggressive tendency of male and female secondary school students using their posttest scores.

Source of variation	SS	df	MS	Cal. F	Pvalue	$P \leq 0.05$
Corrected Model	293.482	4	73.370	3		
Intercept	878.648	1	878.648			
Pretest	170.582	1	170.582			
Gender	2.571	1	2.571		0.03	0.869 NS
Classlevel	1.409	1	1.409		0.02	0.902 NS
Gender * Classlevel	113.809	1	113.809		1.23	0.275 NS
Error	3237.618	35	92.503			
Total	394384.000	40				
Corrected Total	3531.100	39				

Table 5 shows that at 0.05 level of significance, 1df numerator and 39df denominator, the calculated F is 0.03 with Pvalue of 0.869 which is greater than 0.05. Therefore, the second null hypothesis is accepted. So, the effectiveness of self-management technique on aggressive tendency of male and female secondary school students is not significant.

Also in table 5 it was observed that at 0.05 level of significance, 1df numerator and 39df denominator, the calculated F is 0.02 with Pvalue of 0.902 which is greater than 0.05. Therefore, the third null hypothesis is accepted. So, the effectiveness of self-management technique on aggressive tendency of junior and senior secondary school students is not significant.

Again, in table 5 it was observed that at 0.05 level of significance, 1df numerator and 37df denominator, the calculated F is 1.23 with Pvalue of 0.275 which is greater than 0.05. Therefore, the fourth null hypothesis is accepted. So, Self-management technique has no significant interaction effect on aggressive tendency of secondary school students based on their gender and class levels.

Discussion

The first finding from the data analysed in this study indicated that self management technique was effective in reducing aggressive tendency among secondary school students in the treatment group as compared to those in the conventional counselling group. Specifically, the finding revealed that students in both experimental and conventional counselling groups exhibited aggressive tendency prior the commencement of the study as measured by their scores on the pre-test. Shekarey, Ladani and Rostami (2013) observed that aggressive tendency is common in secondary schools. The first finding also indicated that the magnitude of the mean difference between the experimental and conventional counselling groups was significant in the posttest. This finding is in accordance with the reports of many previous researchers (Bongers, Koot, Van & Verhulst, 2007; Ekwe & Nwamuo, 2011; Nyoman, Wayan & Ni, 2017; Oguzie, Obi & Nnadi, 2019; Sincalvin, Calvin, Wehmeyer & Hughes, 2005) who in their respective studies found that self management technique was effective in reducing maladaptive behaviour among students.

One possible reason for the reduction in the aggressive tendency among the students may be that through the self management technique training, the students gained better understanding of the

consequences of their aggressive tendency, and that may have encouraged them to monitor and control their irrational thoughts, emotions and actions. Perhaps, during the experiment, the students acquired the various self management skills that facilitate harmonious interpersonal relations. Supporting the above statement, Betiku (2013) noted that behavioural intervention strategies such as self-management technique have the capacity for guiding individuals towards developing new and acceptable behaviours. Also, Apple, Billingsley and Schwartz (2011) pointed out that self-management technique increases social interactions. Similar, Oguzie, Obi and Nnadi (2019) pointed out that the modification of thought pattern is the goal of every counselling relationship. In line with this, Ekwe and Nwamuo (2011) emphasized that it is imperative that secondary school students are trained in self-management so as to enable them take control of their activities and acquire self-regulatory capacity over their behaviours.

Possibly, during the self-management technique treatment, the students may have become more self-directed and less dependent on continuous supervision. Notably, during the experiment, the students were taught how to monitor and control their thoughts, feelings, emotions and actions. This may have probably affected their level of aggressive tendency to a reasonable extent within the eight weeks of experimentation. Nwosu (2016) noted that in self management training, the participants are given the opportunity to guide, direct and regulate their own thought and behaviour. Self-management technique promotes independence and personal control over behaviour by teaching students how to use behavioral skills for self-treatment (Smith & Sugai, 2000). Since self management training helps clients to achieve adequate self-awareness and self control, perhaps the treatment has encouraged the students to better examine the type, causes and consequences of aggressive tendency.

Another finding of this study is that there was slight gender difference in the effect of self management technique in reducing aggressive tendency among the secondary school students. The result of research question two showed that the decrease in aggressive tendency among female students was slightly higher than that of their male counterparts after they had participated in self management technique treatment. This suggests that the female students seem to have benefited a bit more from self management technique treatment than the male students. This finding is in consonance with the previous findings by (Lansford, Sorbring & Bornstein, 2012; Oguzie, Obi & Nnadi, 2019; Olorufemi & Akomolafe, 2013; Onolemhehem, 2014) who reported that female students benefited more from self-management than their male counterparts. However, the difference in the effect of the technique in this study is small.

Notably, the observed slight difference in the effect of the treatment due to gender was not significant in this study. This is because the test of null hypothesis two showed that there was no significant difference in the reduction of aggressive tendency between male and female students who received self-management technique treatment. Perhaps, the reason for the insignificant difference in the effect of self management technique in reducing aggressive tendency among the secondary school students is because both the male and female students who participated in the self management treatment were given equal

attention in the same condition. During the self management treatment, positive climate was created to ensure free flow of interaction between the male and female students. Enough rapport was built and all the students were treated with unconditional positive regard. This encouraged both the male and female students to participate actively during the experiment. This could mean that all things being equal, both male and female students suffering from aggressive tendency could benefit equally from self management technique regardless of their difference in gender. It therefore means that counsellors should not bother so much on gender difference when using self management technique to self students who with aggressive tendency.

Finally, the findings of this study revealed that there was a difference in the effect of self-management technique on junior and senior secondary students' aggressive tendency. This finding shows that the senior students who participated in the self-management treatment benefited more than their junior counterparts. This particular finding of the study is in-line with the report of previous researchers who found out that senior secondary school students benefited more from self management technique than their junior counterparts (Olorufemi & Akomolafe, 2013; Bongers, Koot & Jans, 2014). In their research Sameer and Jamia (2007) found that SSS students have greater level of aggressive tendency, and are likely to benefit more from intervention treatments than the junior students. One possible reason for the senior students benefiting more than their junior counterparts could be because, the senior students are expected to be more exposed to personal-social situations and have achieved better personal autonomy than their junior counterparts. Moreso, the junior students are more naïve and may still feel inferior in the presence of their seniors no matter the amount of level playing ground provided for them during the experiment. Omotoso (2010) found that older students bully younger ones. This suggests that age difference influences the rate at which secondary school students who are suffering from aggressive tendency benefit from self management technique treatment.

Furthermore, the test of null hypothesis three revealed that there was no significant different in the effect of self-management technique in reducing junior and senior secondary school students' aggressive tendency. The non-significant difference in class level observed in this study could be because the activities provided in the self-management treatment package were designed to assist students' to be able to monitor and manage their thoughts, emotions and behaviours so as to control and inhibit their aggressive tendencies for better and harmonious interrelationships. This means that counsellors may use self management technique to treat aggressive tendency among junior and senior students at the same time.

Conclusions

The study investigated the effect of self-management technique on aggressive tendency among secondary school students in Nnewi North, Anambra State. Based on the findings of this study, the researcher concluded that self-management technique is significantly effective in reducing aggressive

tendency among secondary school students. Secondly, self-management training has no significant gender difference in its effect on aggressive tendency among the students. Also, the difference in the effect of self management technique was not significantly difference based on the students' class level.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. That self-management technique should be used as an effective counselling technique in reducing secondary school students' aggressive tendency. School counsellors should therefore ensure that they acquire adequate knowledge of the technique so as to be able to help students with aggressive tendency.
2. That self-management technique should be used in treating students with aggressive tendency irrespective of their gender and class level. Counsellors should create and provide adequate self management training programmes in form of individual or group counselling for both male and female students suffering from aggressive tendency.
3. That secondary school authorities should create very interesting social programmes for secondary school students so as to enable them interact freely and blend together for more peaceful and harmonious co-existence.
4. That the government should employ enough qualified counsellors who will not have be engaged with tutorial responsibilities but focus mainly on providing effective counselling services to secondary school students.
5. That Anambra State Government should provide all secondary school counsellors with special training programmes on self management technique in form of seminars, conference, workshops or symposia to fully equip them with self management skills and competencies so as to be adequately able to dispense self management training to their students.
6. That the Counselling Association of Nigeria (CASSON), particularly, Anambra State chapter should fashion out enlightenment programs to sensitize secondary school students on the need to consult their school counsellors whenever they feel things are not going on well with them.

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